

IMPROVED AGRICULTURAL MANAGEMENT AND WATER QUALITY IN THE LAKE ERIE WATERSHED

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ABSTRACT

To paraphrase the well-known song, "Lake Erie takes in what her tributaries send her". Managing the coastal zone, of necessity, means managing the watershed. Over the last 20 years, the western Lake Erie watershed has seen many research and demonstration projects to promote agricultural Best Management Practices, and important changes have occurred in the way the land is used. These include adoption of conservation tillage on 50% of the row crop acreage, and substantial reductions in fertilizer use (including manure), particularly the phosphorus component. At the same time, substantial and statistically significant downward trends have been detected in the Maumee and Sandusky rivers, in sediment, phosphorus, and some forms of nitrogen. Various lines of evidence argue that these water quality improvements are primarily due to changes in agricultural management.

Recently, the Conservation Reserve Enhancement Program has been implemented in Ohio, with the goals of 1) protecting 10% of stream miles in the western Lake Erie watersheds with filter strips and riparian buffers, and 2) reducing annual sediment loads from these watersheds by 150,000 metric tons over 10 years, saving 825,000 metric tons of sediment in that time, and 2,325,000 metric tons over 20 years. This project should further reduce loads of sediment and associated nutrients to Lake Erie.

INTRODUCTION

In the 1960s and early 1970s, Lake Erie was frequently referred to as a "dead lake." Excessive phosphorus loading led to eutrophication and summertime anoxia in the open waters of the Central Basin. The first line of attack on this problem was to reduce loadings from point sources discharging directly to the lake. Agricultural lands were identified as an additional significant source of phosphorus from which loadings would need to be reduced. Demonstration projects in the 1970s led to major implementation programs in the 1980s, designed to foster basin-wide adoption of conservation tillage and other agricultural management practices to reduce erosion and the transport of sediment and particulate phosphorus into Lake Erie. These programs and other factors have brought about major changes in agricultural practices.

The Water Quality Laboratory at Heidelberg College has been monitoring water quality since 1969 near the mouths of the two largest U.S. tributaries to Lake Erie, the Maumee and Sandusky rivers (at USGS gaging stations at Waterville and Fremont, respectively), with daily and more frequent samples. The resulting data sets are ideally suited for the

study of water quality responses to changing agricultural practices. The USDA-funded Lake Erie Agricultural Systems for Environmental Quality (LEASEQ) project was conceived as a retrospective examination of changes in agriculture practices and their impacts on water and soil quality and agricultural outputs. The study area comprises the watersheds of the Maumee and Sandusky rivers, and is located mostly in northwest Ohio but includes portions of northeast Indiana and southern Michigan. The study period is the years 1975-1995. In this paper we summarize LEASEQ findings about trends in agriculture and in water quality, and about the relationship between the two. A more detailed treatment of these topics is available on request from the first author.

METHODS

County-level agricultural statistics were obtained from appropriate state agencies and from the Conservation Tillage Information Center at Purdue University. These statistics were aggregated for the watersheds upstream from the water quality stations. Statistics for counties that lie on the watershed boundary were allocated to the watershed in proportion with the percent of the county area within the watershed. Trends were examined visually and quantified by linear regression or in some cases by fitting a LOWESS smoothed curve to the data (Cleveland, 1979).

Water quality data for sediments and nutrients were aggregated to a daily load basis using USGS mean daily flows and daily average concentrations. The daily load series were examined for trends using an ANCOVA procedure that adjusted results for the influence of flow and seasonality on concentrations, an approach similar to that recommended by Hirsch et al. (1991). In addition, non-linear trends were evaluated using LOWESS smooths, to determine when loads were changing most rapidly.

RESULTS

Results were calculated for each watershed separately, but they are generally quite similar. In the interest of conciseness, results are presented below as aggregates for the study area as a whole.

Several important trends in the use of agricultural lands were recognized:

- Farm size increased by more than 40% but the number of farms decreased by more than 33%; net change in farm land was about -7.5%
- Row-crop agriculture dominated agricultural land use throughout the period; soybeans was the major crop (in terms of land use) and increased about 15%, corn was second and decreased about 10%, wheat was third and decreased about 14%, hay was a distant fourth and decreased by about 30%
- Crop yields (on a per-acre basis) increased for all crops: soybeans by 16%, corn by 20%, and wheat and hay by about 30%.
- The number of Animal Units decreased, particularly cattle, dairy cows, and sheep. As a result, manure production from farm animals decreased by more than 20%

- Fertilizer sales peaked in the early 1980's and have decreased since then, phosphorus by about 35% and nitrogen by 28%. However, nitrogen sales show a net increase over the entire period of record of about 30%
- Conservation tillage, virtually unknown at the start of the study period, increased to about 50% of the tilled acres by 1995. The major share of this is due to no-till soybeans. About 5% of all farmland was in the Conservation Reserve Program as of 1995. In the last year, the Conservation Reserve Enhancement Program (CREP) has started in these watersheds, and enrollment has been ahead of schedule.

There have also been substantial trends in water quality during the study period:

- Flow appears to have increased by about 8%, but the change is not statistically significant
- Suspended sediment has decreased by about 22%
- Total phosphorus has decreased by more than 40%, and soluble reactive phosphorus by about 85%
- Total Kjeldahl nitrogen (organic nitrogen + ammonia) has decreased by about 25%, while nitrate has increased by about 17%
- All trends in nutrients and sediment are highly significant statistically with the exception of the increase in nitrate, which is not significant. All trends are consistent in direction and comparable in magnitude for both watersheds.

DISCUSSION

Temporal coincidence of land use and water quality trends does not prove causality. Several other observations are important in this respect. Climate trends in this period of time are minor in all aspects, and cannot be an important cause of the water quality trends. Point sources upstream from the sampling stations are minor contributors to observed loads, never more than 15%; while they have decreased, the change is far too small to account for the water quality trends. Row-crop agriculture dominates the landscape and hence the nonpoint-source process in these watersheds. The timing of water quality improvements coordinates well with the history of fertilizer sales and manure production and with the advent of conservation tillage. All of these lines of evidence support the hypothesis that the water quality changes were indeed largely *caused* by changes in agricultural practices.

The linkage between the lake and its tributaries is complex, because of processing that occurs in Sandusky Bay and to a lesser extent in Maumee Bay. While improvements in tributary water quality must contribute to improved water quality in Lake Erie, the details are poorly understood and need study, particularly in the post-zebra mussel era.

There is now concern among some interested observers that phosphorus levels in Lake Erie may fall too low. The CREP program may well reduce sediment losses from Ohio watersheds by substantially more than the target 10%. With these reductions in sediment will certainly come further reductions in phosphorus loads. We can begin to foresee the time when immutable connections between water quality constituents (such as sediment and phosphorus) may lead to conflicts in water quality management goals. Such conflicts will be a sure sign that we have been successful in our goal of rehabilitating our “dead lake”!

CONCLUSIONS

The LEASEQ project has documented substantial changes in agricultural practices in voluntary response to agricultural technology transfer programs, economic incentive programs, and unplanned changes in the farm economy; many of these changes would be expected to have an impact on water quality in adjacent rivers and streams. During the same period, significant reductions occurred in concentrations and loads of suspended sediment, total and soluble phosphorus, and total Kjeldahl nitrogen. Nitrate, a parameter not targeted for management, appears to have increased during the same period. Most of these water quality changes are in the direction expected as a consequence of the agricultural management changes. The synchronous nature of changes in agricultural and water quality parameters, and the lack of other major phosphorus and sediment sources in the study area, supports the hypothesis that the improvements in water quality were caused primarily by the changes in agricultural practices.

The quality of water in Lake Erie, even in the coastal zone, bears a complex relationship to that in the tributaries, but improvements of this sort in major tributaries are certainly an important contributor to the improved water quality in Lake Erie itself.

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